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Nanocomposite gels of poloxamine and Laponite for β -Lapachone release in anticancer therapy
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Abstract:	Nano-hybrid systems have been shown to be an attractive platform for drug delivery. Laponite® RD (LAP), a biocompatible synthetic clay, has been exploited for its ability to establish of strong secondary interactions with guest compounds and hybridization with polymers or small molecules that improves, for instance, cell adhesion, proliferation, and differentiation or facilitates drug attachment to their surfaces through charge interaction. In this work, LAP was combined with Tetronics, X-shaped amphiphilic PPO-PEO (poly (propylene oxide)-poly (ethylene oxide) block copolymers. β -Lapachone (BLPC) was selected for its anticancer activity and its limited bioavailability due to very low aqueous solubility, with the aim to improve this by using LAP/Tetronic nano-hybrid systems. The nanocarriers were prepared over a range of Tetronic 1304 concentrations (1 to 20% w/w) and LAP (0 to 3% w/w). A combination of physicochemical methods was employed to characterize the hybrid systems, including rheology, particle size and shape (DLS, TEM), thermal analysis (TG and DSC), FTIR, solubility studies and drug release experiments. In vitro cytotoxicity assays were performed with BALB/3T3 and MCF-7 cell lines. In hybrid systems, a sol-gel transition can occur below physiological temperature. BLPC exhibits the most significant increase in solubility in formulations with a high concentration of T1304 (over 10% w/w) and 1.5% w/w LAP, or systems with only LAP (1.5%), with a 50 and 100-fold increase in solubilisation, respectively. TEM images showed spherical micelles of T1304, which elongated into wormlike micelles with concentration (20%) and in the presence of LAP, a finding that has not been reported before. A sustained release of BLPC over 140 hours was achieved in one of the formulations (10% T1304 with 1.5% laponite), which also showed the best selectivity index towards cancer cells (MCF-7) over BALB/3T3 cell lines. In conclusion, BLPC-loaded T1304/LAP nano-hybrid systems proved safe and highly effective and are thus a promising formulation for anticancer therapy.

1 **Nanocomposite gels of poloxamine and Laponite for β -Lapachone release in**
2 **anticancer therapy**

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1 **Abstract**

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3 **Laponite® RD (LAP), a biocompatible synthetic clay, has been exploited for its ability**
4 **to establish of strong secondary interactions with guest compounds and hybridization**
5 **with polymers or small molecules that improves, for instance, cell adhesion,**
6 **proliferation, and differentiation or facilitates drug attachment to their surfaces through**
7 **charge interaction.** In this work, LAP was combined with Tetronics, X-shaped
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9 copolymers. β -Lapachone (BLPC) was selected for its anticancer activity and its limited
10 bioavailability due to very low aqueous solubility, with the aim to improve this by using
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29 **Key words:** Micelles; β -Lapachone; **Laponite** RD; Tetronic T1304, Thermoresponsive
30 Gels, solubilization; drug delivery.

1. Introduction

Poloxamines, commercially available as Tetronic, consist of block copolymers of polyethylene oxide (PEO) and polypropylene oxide (PPO). Unlike Pluronic, where the blocks are **disposed** in a linear fashion, Tetratics blocks are arranged as 4-arm star-shaped chains linked together by a central ethylenediamine group [1,2], which imparts pH-responsiveness to the polymers.

PEO-PPO-PEO copolymers display a wide spectrum of molecular weights (MW) and ethylene oxide/Propylene oxide (EO/PO) ratios [3], being classified as highly hydrophilic (T908, T1107 and T1307), or of median hydrophilicity (T304, T904 and T1304) and c) highly hydrophobic (T701, T901, T1301, T90R4 and T150R1) [4]. Due to their amphiphilicity, Tetratics are able to form micelles above a threshold temperature and concentration, and this self-assembly is pH dependent [5–8]. pH and temperature alter the size and structure of Tetronic micelles, influence the sol-to-gel transition, giving rise to a rich phase behavior determined by **the** specific molecular architecture **of the system** and **the Tetronic** HLB (hydrophilic-lipophilic balance), and therefore provide attractive features for **drug** delivery to a specific target [9,10]. Cytocompatibility, without significant irritation after topical or parenteral administration has been described [11].

The core-shell structure of the micelles enables them to solubilise hydrophobic drugs, while the highly hydrated PEO chains stabilize the structure, reducing adsorption and adhesion to cell surfaces, decreasing opsonization from the mononuclear phagocytic system [8,12–14]. In addition, PEO–PPO-based polymeric micelles also present a size adequate for passive targeting within a tumor, and a biological inhibitory activity of drug efflux pumps, in particular the ability to inhibit ATP-binding cassette transporters in cancer cell lines, responsible for multidrug resistance (MDR) [15][3].

A few previous studies on T1304 have shown its potential in the pharmaceutical field. T1304 has an average molecular weight of 10,500 Dalton and 21.4 and 27.1 EO and PO units per arm, respectively, with a HLB between 12–18. Pillai et al. 2016 [16] studied the self-assembly of T1304 in water and aqueous salt solutions, showing a significant influence of the presence of salt on the micellar structure in modulating the core-shell morphology, enhancing the solubilization of hydrophobic drugs (quercetin and curcumin), and affecting cytotoxicity. In another study, Patel et al. 2019 [17] showed the solubilization of three pharmaceutical antioxidants (hydrocinnamic acid, cinnamic acid, and phenyl propiolic acid) in T1304 micelles. The authors demonstrated the role of antioxidants on the modulation of the core-shell micelles at 5% w/v with enhanced solubility (dependent on their unsaturation and hydrophobicity). The antioxidant loaded T1304 exhibited a substantial biocidal activity against *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, and *A. niger*, mainly for T1304 micelles with phenyl propiolic acid.

Clays are hydrated aluminosilicate minerals with plastic properties when mixed with water. Among their numerous useful properties, their high specific surface area makes them extremely useful in industrial processes where solid-solid interactions are involved, such as in ion exchangers and as viscosity modifiers [18–20]. Specifically, Laponite RD (LAP) is a swelling **and biocompatible** nano-clay, composed of layered synthetic phyllosilicates with an octahedral MgO sheet sandwiched between two tetrahedral silica sheets and a chemical formula given by: $\text{Si}_8\text{Mg}_{5.45}\text{Li}_{0.4}\text{O}_{24}\text{Na}_{0.7}$; it is widely used as a mechanical cross-linker to create hydrogels with robust mechanical properties [21,22]. LAP on its own can also be used as a rheological modifier due to its ability to form gels when dispersed in polar solvents such as water [23]. This ability can be explained by its lamellar, disc-like shape (ca. 25 nm diameter and 1 nm in thickness) with negative charges distributed on the faces (OH^-) and positive charges on the edges (Na^+), and involves a multi-step mechanism. Initially, the particles react with hydroxide

1 ions in water. After ion dissolution, the nano-clay particles interact with each other and
2 sodium ions diffuse to the surfaces of the galleries formed, resulting in an expanded
3 thixotropic gel, with a “house-of-cards” structure [24]. LAP **interacts** with charged,
4 polar, and nonpolar species. This interaction is due to its large charged surface, which
5 enables the adsorption of ions or molecules through ion exchange, van der Waals forces,
6 hydrogen bonding, and cation/water bridges, as well as protonation and ligand exchange
7 at the edges of the crystal [19]. **The degradation of LAP occurs particularly under acidic**
8 **conditions promoting aqueous silica release (Si (OH)₄ [25].**

9 Nano-hybrid systems can be defined as synthetic materials formed by the combination
10 of organic and inorganic nanometric compounds through non-covalent interactions
11 (linked by hydrogen bonding, electrostatic or van der Waals forces) or covalent bonds
12 [26], which results in the synergistic enhancement of their functional properties. Nano-
13 hybrids systems are a powerful tool to develop new platforms for drug delivery, and
14 stimuli-responsive smart materials [27].

15 We expect that the combination of Tetronic’s thermoresponsive properties with the
16 swelling capacity of LAP will generate polymer-clay nano-hybrids that offer drug
17 solubilisation capacity, and are potentially injectable if the sol-gel transition can be
18 tuned to just below body temperature. LAP provides a handle to tune the sol-gel
19 transition and the rheological properties of both phases (liquid and gel), while offering
20 an additional locus for drug attachment [28,29]. **These systems could be interesting as**
21 **intramuscular depot formulations.**

22 Quinones represent a large family of natural metabolites produced by plants and insects
23 as a defence against external aggressors [30]. Among the natural naphthoquinones,
24 Lapachol is an important secondary metabolite that can be found in large quantities in
25 the wood of the *Tabebuia* genus [31]. Lapachol and its derivatives such as α and β -
26 Lapachone (BLPC) have potential applications in the medical field and interest in this
27 compound has increased in the past decade mainly as antiparasitic, anti-cancer and
28 antiviral drugs. The antiparasitic action was demonstrated against *Trypanosoma cruzi*
29 [32], *Plasmodium*[33], and *Leishmania* [34]. Moreover, antiviral action against HIV,
30 and human polyomavirus 2 [35,36] was also found. The antineoplastic action of BLPC
31 has been proposed for prostate, breast, and lung cancer treatment [37–39]. However,
32 BLPC has low solubility in water [40], which limits its administration, bioavailability
33 and clinical applications *in vivo*. In addition, its biodegradation after passage through
34 the liver (first pass effect) greatly reduces the fraction of BLPC that arrives unmodified
35 into the systemic circulation when administered orally [41], which represents another
36 hurdle for BLPC bioavailability.

37 The objective of the work was to prepare, characterize and compare different
38 formulations based on the combination of Tetronic 1304 (organic), and Laponite
39 (inorganic network), to increase the solubility and bioavailability of BLPC. Physico-
40 chemical characterization, *in vitro* release kinetics, biocompatibility and anticancer
41 activity tests were performed to assess the different hybrid systems.

42 43 **1. Materials and Methods**

44 **2.1 Materials**

45 Tetronic 1304 (T1304) and Laponite RD (LAP) were donated by BASF Corporation
46 (Ludwigshafen, Germany) and BYK Additives & Instruments (Wesel, Germany),
47 respectively. BLPC was synthesized from Lapachol, by acidic cyclization with sulphuric
48 acid at low temperatures (Scheme 1) [42,43]. The rest of the chemicals used in this
49 research were of analytical grade and commercially available.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of the BLPC by cyclization of Lapachol in acidic medium and room temperature.

2.2. Preparation of the nano-hybrids

The nanocomposites were prepared by adding LAP to water under constant stirring and adding Tetronic after 20 minutes and then leaving to stir for 24 hours. All samples were made in triplicates. Table 1 shows the concentrations used, ranging from 1-20% (w/w) and LAP (0, 1.5 and 3%, w/w) of samples prepared.

<Insert Table 1>

Table 1. Samples studied in this work comprising the polymeric surfactant Tetronic T1304 with and without LAP, with concentrations ranging from 1-20% Tetronic and 0, 1.5 and 3% LAP.

Formulation		CODE
T1304 %, w/w	LAP %, w/w	
0	1.5	1.5LAP
0	3	3LAP
1	0	T1
5	0	T5
10	0	T10
15	0	T15
20	0	T20
1	1.5	T1/1.5LAP
5	1.5	T5/1.5LAP
10	1.5	T10/1.5LAP
15	1.5	T15/1.5LAP
20	1.5	T20/1.5LAP
1	3.0	T1/3LAP
5	3.0	T5/3LAP
10	3.0	T10/3LAP
15	3.0	T15/3LAP
20	3.0	T20/3LAP

2.3 Characterization of the nanocarriers

2.3.1 BLPC solubility studies

The nanocarrier systems (single and hybrid systems, Table 1) were introduced in vials to evaluate the maximum solubility of BLPC. Supersaturated BLPC solutions were prepared by adding 5 mg of drug in vials (n=6). **The samples were stirred for ten days**

1 uninterrupted using Blood Homogenizer and Solutions Model AP 22 (Phoenix-Luferco,
2 Araraquara, SP, Brazil). The samples were centrifuged (14,000 rpm for 15 min at 20
3 °C). Drug concentration in the supernatants was quantified by UV-Vis
4 spectrophotometry (Varian Cary® 50 UV-Vis, Palo Alto, California, USA) at 257 nm
5 using each system composition as a blank, and the molar absorptivities established
6 previously with the Beer-Lambert law (Supplementary material, S1). The data are
7 expressed as the mean of three experiments (n) ± standard deviation (sd). BLPC
8 concentration was assessed using the linear equation established: $abs = 0.1123 \times C_{BLPC}$
9 $+ 0.0041$ (where *abs* is the measured absorbance of the solution and C_{BLPC} is the drug
10 concentration with $R^2 = 0.9998$), obtained from BLPC absorbance in ethanolic solution
11 ($2\text{-}10 \mu\text{g.mL}^{-1}$) standard curve [40]. The same curve was used to measure the BLPC
12 concentration in the systems.

13 14 **2.3.2 Phase diagrams**

15 All samples were placed into a water bath that was set initially to a temperature of 20
16 °C, which was gradually increased by 5 °C increments up to a maximum of 80 °C (Table
17 1). The phase behaviour of the samples was observed at 10-minute intervals at each
18 temperature. All samples were made in triplicates at their natural pH (~8.2 for samples
19 without LAP and ~10 for samples with LAP) [8,44].

20 21 **2.3.3 Rheological behaviour**

22 The rheological properties of T10/1.5LAP and T20/1.5LAP with and without BLPC
23 were determined using a dynamic voltage-controlled rheometer (Kinexus Lab, Malvern
24 Instruments Ltd, Worcestershire, UK), equipped with parallel plates (40 mm) geometry.
25 Temperature sweeps were performed over the temperature range 20 °C to 60 °C, at 5
26 °C.min⁻¹. The elastic and viscous moduli of the systems (G' and G'' , respectively) were
27 measured by using a frequency of 1 Hz, shear stress of 2 Pa, and a gap of 1 mm. Samples
28 containing BLPC were measured using the maximum solubility obtained from the
29 solubility studies.

30 31 **2.3.4 Dynamic light scattering (DLS)**

32 Size distributions and polydispersity of the samples T1, T5 and T10 were analysed using
33 a temperature ramp (from 20 to 60 °C with 5 °C intervals) by dynamic light scattering
34 (DLS, Malvern Instruments Inc., Malvern, UK) with a laser wavelength of 633 nm. Prior
35 to the measurements, the samples were filtered using 0.22 μm Millex filters (Millipore,
36 Burlington, MA, USA) and added in semi-micro glass cells. The temperature was
37 controlled with a precision of 0.1 °C by the Peltier unit incorporated in the cell
38 compartment.

39 40 **2.3.5 Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM)**

41 Selected formulations were studied by TEM. Formulations T10 and T20 with and
42 without LAP were immediately placed over a SiO₂ copper grid (200 mesh) and
43 negatively stained with uranyl acetate (1%, pH 7.0) to fix the samples at 20 °C [45]. The
44 structure of the samples was observed under a Libra 120 PLUS (Carl Zeiss, Weimar,
45 Germany) equipped with EELS (resolution < 1.5 eV). The identification and localization
46 of LAP in the T20/LAP sample was performed by High-Resolution Transmission
47 Electron Microscope (HRTEM, FEI TITAN G2) coupled with a SUPER-X silicon-drift
48 windowless Energy-Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) detector. The spectra were
49 collected in STEM mode (Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy) using a
50 HAADF (High Angle Annular Dark Field) method. The diameter of the
51 micelles/aggregates was measured using a calibrated scale.

2.3.6 Thermal analysis

Conventional thermal analysis techniques, thermogravimetry (TG) and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), were used for the characterization of LAP1.5, T10, T20, T10/1.5LAP and T20/1.5LAP with and without BLPC. Except for BLPC, all samples were freeze-dried prior to the TG and DSC. The freeze-drying process was performed in a Christ Alpha 1-2 apparatus (Martin Christ Freeze-dryers, Osterode am Harz Germany) after subjecting formulations to -20 °C for 6 hours. The thermal analysis included TG and DSC. TG was performed on a TG-60 (Shimadzu, Chiyoda-ku, Tokyo Japan) under a nitrogen atmosphere with a heating rate of 10 °C·min⁻¹ and a flow rate of 10 mL·min⁻¹, from 25 °C to 600 °C. DSC measurements were carried out using a DSC-50 (Shimadzu, Chiyoda-ku, Tokyo Japan). All samples were placed in aluminium sample holders and heated at a rate of 10 mL·min⁻¹ from 25 °C to 450 °C under nitrogen flow (10 mL·min⁻¹). The addition of BLPC-containing samples was done at the maximum solubility as obtained from the solubility assay.

2.3.7 Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

FTIR spectra were obtained for samples T10, T20, T10/1.5LAP and T20/1.5LAP using a device equipped with attenuated total reflectance (ATR) of the IR Prestige-21 model (Shimadzu, Chiyoda-ku, Tokyo Japan). 20 scans were performed per sample within the range 4000 cm⁻¹ to 700 cm⁻¹ [46]. The pH of samples with LAP were adjusted to pH 9.0 with hydrochloric acid (due to requirements of the IR Prestige-21).

2.3.8 *In vitro* release kinetics of BLPC

The release of BLPC from the T10/1.5LAP nanocomposites was studied in a Sotax AT7 (Sotax, Aesch, Switzerland). The initial concentration (0.5 mg·mL⁻¹) of BLPC at the T10/1.5LAP system corresponds one-third below the maximum BLPC solubility in this system (essential to ensure the sink condition). A total volume of 200 mL phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH 7.4) was used as a release medium. The whole medium was maintained at 37 °C and stirred at 100 rpm with a basket system, in which a 1kDa Mini Dialysis (GE Healthcare Bio-Sciences Corp., Piscataway, NJ, USA) membrane device containing the formulation was placed. At predetermined intervals, 0.5 mL of release medium was withdrawn and subsequently replenished with fresh PBS in order to ensure sink conditions. The release study was performed over a maximum of 140 hours (ca. 6 days). For comparison purposes, free BLPC was diluted in deionized water at its maximum concentration (0.038 mg·mL⁻¹, its own solubility limit in water) in a 1 kDa membrane, which, in turn, was placed in the basket system of the equipment. BLPC was quantified by UV-visible spectrophotometry, as mentioned in section 2.3.1. All experiments were carried out in triplicates and data are expressed as mean ± sd [28].

To understand the release mechanism, the percentage of cumulative BLPC released was fitted to various mathematical models, where four with the best fit were chosen for analysis: zero and first order, Higuchi, Korsmeyer-Peppas, Hixson-Crowell, Hopfenberg, Peppas-Sahlin and Weibull, using the DDSolver[®] [47,48].

The Weibull model (WM), a statistical model adapted for drug release by Langenbucher, 1972, includes a time scale parameter α and a parameter β related to the shape, which characterizes the release mechanism. For $\beta < 1$, simple Fickian diffusion drives the drug release, if $\beta = 1$, the release kinetics follows a first order model, and for $\beta > 1$ there are more than two forces governing the release.

The model proposed by Peppas-Sahlin combines two driving forces for the release process: the first is the drug release by simple Fickian diffusion from a polymer matrix, represented by a constant ks_1 , and the relaxation of the polymer chains, represented by

1 the constant k_s . The Hixson-Crowell model evaluates the drug release due to erosion of
2 carrier molecules, leading to changes in the surface area and/or diameter of the particles. The
3 Hopfenberg models a polymeric matrix that undergoes erosion, either through the
4 formation of new chemical bonds when in contact with the drug release medium, or by
5 drug dissolution in the release medium, leaving only the dry polymeric matrix at the end
6 of the process; a shape parameter “n” was introduced, which can acquire the values of
7 1 for beads, 2 for cylinders and 3 for spheres [48].

9 2.3.9 Cytotoxicity of the formulations

10 Cytotoxicity tests were performed on selected BALB/3T3 clone A31 embryonic
11 fibroblasts from mice (*Mus Musculus*) and human adenocarcinoma cells from mammary
12 glands, MCF-7. Both were obtained from the Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, Cell Bank (BCRJ).
13 3T3 cells (a noncarcinogenic cell line) were cultured in Dulbecco's modified Eagle's
14 medium with 4 mmol.L⁻¹ L-glutamine adjusted to contain 1.5 g.L⁻¹ sodium bicarbonate
15 and 4.5 g.L⁻¹ glucose and supplemented with 5 mmol.L⁻¹ HEPES (Sigma-Aldrich®, St.
16 Louis, MO, USA), bovine calf serum to a final concentration of 10% (Sigma-Aldrich®,
17 St. Louis, MO, USA) and 1% (v/v) antibiotic antimycotic solution (100×) (Sigma-
18 Aldrich®, St. Louis, MO, USA) [49]. MCF-7 was grown in RPMI-1640 medium
19 modified to contain 2 mmol.L⁻¹ L-glutamine, 10 mmol.L⁻¹ HEPES, 1 mmol.L⁻¹ sodium
20 pyruvate, 4500 mg.L⁻¹ glucose, and 1500 mg.L⁻¹ sodium bicarbonate and 20% of fetal
21 bovine serum [50,51]. The cells were kept in a humidified atmosphere of 5% CO₂ in air
22 at 37 °C.

23 Cytotoxicity of the formulations was evaluated over the cultured cells submitted to the
24 MTT assay [3- (4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl) -2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide], which is
25 able to assess cell viability by converting the tetrazolium salt into formazan crystals, due
26 to the mitochondrial activity of cells. 50 µL of MTT was added to each well with a
27 concentration of 1 mg.mL⁻¹.

28 Cultures of 3T3 or MCF-7 were prepared in 96-well tissue culture plates (10⁴ cells well⁻¹).
29 After 24 hours, the cells were incubated with BLPC at 8; 6; 4; and 2 µmol.L⁻¹ and the
30 formulations (1.5LAP, T10/1.5LAP, and T20/1.5LAP) with and without drug. The
31 systems were diluted to obtain the BLPC concentrations of 8; 6; 4; and 2 µmol.L⁻¹. Drug-
32 free formulations were also diluted in the same manner to compare their cytotoxicity
33 with BLPC systems.

34 After this step, the microplate was subjected to a new incubation for 24 hours and, later,
35 the MTT was added to the microplate and incubated for 4 hours. Finally, 100 µL of
36 DMSO was added to each well for dissolution of the formazan crystals produced due to
37 the reduction of the dye. The microplate was subjected to vigorous stirring for complete
38 solubilization of the crystals. Each well was read in a spectrophotometer with a
39 wavelength of 540 nm, in an Epoch Microplate Spectrophotometer (Biotek, Winooski,
40 VT, USA). For all formulations, an exponential curve of concentration versus cell
41 viability was plotted and its equation obtained, which gave the value of IC₅₀ (the
42 required concentration of drug to decrease cell viability by 50%).

44 2.3.10 Statistical Analysis

45 Statistical data analysis was performed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA)
46 among groups with subsequent Tukey t-test with a significance level of 5% (p < 0.05).
47 The data were calculated using Prism 6® (Graphpad Software 2012, San Diego,
48 California, USA).

50 3. Results and Discussion

51 3.1 Solubility of BLPC in the nano-hybrid systems

1 The aqueous solubility of BLPC was determined previously by our group to be 0.038
 2 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ [40,52]. Fig. 1 shows the solubility of BLPC in a range of formulations.
 3 Solubilisation of BLPC is achieved by Tetronic, with a significant enhancement
 4 obtained by the addition of LAP, particularly at 1.5%. Enhancement of solubility is
 5 particularly visible in the 1.5 LAP formulation without polymer, where the improvement
 6 is 100-fold, while it is 42 times with 20% poloxamine (T20/1.5LAP), and about 6 times
 7 with 1% Tetronic alone (T1). BLPC may both solubilise inside the polymer micelles, as
 8 well as between clay layers [53]. LAP binding sites allow the solubilisation of drugs
 9 within the spacing between LAP nanodisks through ion exchange. Previous studies have
 10 demonstrated for instance the encapsulation of doxorubicin in LAP nanodisks [54].
 11 It is noticeable that the higher LAP concentration of 3% (w/w) impacts drug solubility
 12 to a lower extent than 1.5% (w/w), which can be attributed to the formation of
 13 aggregates of LAP nanodisks, hindering entrance of the drug into the interlamellar
 14 spaces [55,56]. On the lower solubility of BLPC obtained when adding Tetronic to LAP,
 15 this could be explained by a disruption of the LAP network with the polymer, and its
 16 adsorption on LAP, which may therefore compete with LAP-drug interactions.

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<Insert Fig. 1>

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Fig. 1. Solubility of BLPC in formulations of T1304, LAP and their combination over a range of concentrations, at room temperature. For hybrid systems (n) corresponds to T1304 concentration and * represents the statistical difference between the groups with $p < 0.05$. (n=6, mean \pm sd).

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3.2 Rheological behaviour

Two formulations, T20/1.5LAP and T10/1.5LAP, were selected for rheological studies in view of their high solubilisation capacity added to their gel state at physiological temperature. Fig. 2 reports shear oscillatory temperature sweeps performed on the systems, showing the storage (G') and loss (G'') moduli over the range 20 to 60°C. For both nanohybrid systems, G' and G'' show a marked increase just above 25°C for T10/1.5LAP and above 20°C for the more concentrated system (T20/1.5LAP), reflecting a sol-gel transition, which is corroborated by the visual observation of the samples (shown above each graph). The elastic modulus reaches values around 10,600 Pa for T10/1.5LAP and 4,300 Pa for T20/1.5LAP. The presence of drug leads to a

1 marginal increase in the values of the moduli and shifts the sol-gel transition to slightly
 2 lower temperatures. The complete phase behaviour of the samples is provided in Fig. 3.

3
 4 <Insert Fig. 2>

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6

7 Fig. 2. Rheology temperature sweeps showing the elastic (G') and viscous (G'') moduli
 8 for two formulations with and without BLPC. A) T10/1.5LAP. B) T20/1.5LAP. The
 9 chart above each graph illustrates the phase behavior of the systems obtained from visual
 10 observation. BLPC was incorporated at the maximum solubility obtained from the
 11 solubility tests ($0.75 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ and $1.5 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$, respectively).

12

13 <Insert Fig. 3>

Legend of phase behavior:

- Liquid
- Viscous liquid
- Gel
- Strong gel
- Solid

Legend: **Liquid:** liquid formulations are clear aqueous dispersions unable to hold their weight against gravity in an inverted vial. **Viscous liquid:** viscous liquid formulations are thicker liquids: liquid flow occurs more slowly and is still unable to hold its weight against gravity in an inverted vial. **Gel:** gel formulations are clear gel dispersions and able to hold their weight against gravity in an inverted vial but come off when shaken. **Strong gel:** strong gel formulations are clear gel dispersions and able to hold their weight against gravity in an inverted vial but do not come off when shaken. **Solid:** Phase separation leading to a solid cluster suspended in the fluid.

Fig. 3. The physical behavior of formulations at different concentrations after 1 week at natural pH (~10) and at different temperatures.

Interestingly, none of the individual systems (10% or 20% T1304 or 1.5% LAP) undergoes transition to gel state over this temperature range (only 3% LAP forms a gel at all temperatures, and 1.5%LAP at very high temperatures, Fig. 3), it is therefore the polymer-clay interaction that gives rise to a viscoelastic network. This transition has been observed before in mixtures of Pluronic F127 with laponite [57] and gelation was attributed to several possible mechanisms, including the adsorption of the polymers on the laponite disks (as confirmed by small-angle neutron scattering studies), and these layers becoming “sticky” with temperature, or, more likely, a depletion flocculation of the laponite particles induced by free polymer micelles.

3.3 Dynamic light scattering (DLS)

The micellization behaviour of T1304 was assessed by DLS over a range of temperatures (Fig. 4). The data show the typical profile of Tetronics: namely, at low temperatures (20 °C), the presence of a “unimer” peak (with 4.3 ± 1.0 nm hydrodynamic diameter), which shifts to higher values with temperature, reflecting micellization (with a diameter of ca. 13.9 ± 0.5 nm). The peak at very high values is attributed to impurities, which become solubilised in the micelles, and are typical of Pluronic and Tetronic samples as observed by Puig-Rigall and co-authors [8]. These sizes are approximately twice larger than obtained for Tetronic 908, which bears a similar number of PO (21 units per arm) but has much longer PEO chains (114 EO units per arm) [8]. Pillai et al

- 1 (2019) reported similar sizes for T1304 micelles with a diameter of 14.20 nm at 30 °C
- 2 [58].
- 3 <Insert Fig. 4>

(A)

(B)

4 Fig. 4. Intensity (%) size distributions of T1304 micelles as a function of temperature
 5 (in °C) obtained by DLS in H₂O (Milli-Q). In (A) T1, and (B) T10 formulations.

6

7 3.4 Transmission Electron Microscopy

8 Fig. 5 presents the morphologies of both Tetronic micelles (T10 and T20) and their
 9 mixtures with laponite (T10/1.5LAP and T20/1.5LAP). Tetronic micelles appear as
 10 white dots, either spherical (Fig. 5A) or slightly elongated structures (Fig. 5B). Spherical
 11 micelles have an average size of 8 nm (diameter), and the cylindrical micelles shown in
 12 Fig. 5B have an average width of 11 nm with different lengths, in good agreement with
 13 the DLS data. An increase in T1304 concentration (from 10 to 20%, Fig. 5B), or the

1 presence of LAP in the T10/1.5LAP (Fig. 5C) promotes the formation of cylindrical
2 micelles, particularly elongated in the presence of LAP. TEM images of T20/1.5LAP
3 at 20 °C (Fig. 5D) show cylindrical micelles over 100 nm in length, some with junctions.
4 The mean cylinder width is relatively well-defined and can be estimated as 18-20 nm;
5 these coexist with polydisperse spheroidal nanoparticles (20 -70nm).

6 The physical state of formulations at different concentrations at 20°C and natural pH is
7 represented in Fig. 5G. The free-flowing samples, namely, T10, T20, and T10/1.5LAP,
8 contain spherical or short cylindrical micelles, while T20/1.5LAP is a gel at room
9 temperature and contains longer cylindrical micelles (Fig. 5G).

10 **EDX results performed by HRTEM** (Fig. 5E and F) confirm the presence of LAP by the
11 detection of silicon and magnesium and allowed the identification of some clay particles
12 in the T20/1.5LAP formulation (red arrow, Fig. 5E) outside the micellar structures
13 (longer cylindrical micelles or spherical micelles).

14 To our knowledge, this is the first time that long cylindrical micelles of Tetronic are
15 reported. The further elongation of these structures into flexible aggregates, or wormlike
16 micelles, in the presence of laponite is also unreported. These exquisite structures, with
17 very well-defined width, could also explain the viscoelastic properties of the materials
18 (if the micelles are long enough to entangle). These flexible aggregates are widely used
19 in personal care and household products [59], but are also attractive for emerging
20 applications as drug delivery vehicles, where shape could improve loading and targeting
21 [60].

22
23 <Insert Fig. 5>

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Fig. 5. Representative TEM and HRTEM images and of micellar morphologies observed after drying an aqueous dispersion at 20 °C. TEM images of: (A) T10 (B) T20, (C) T10/1.5LAP (D) T20/1.5LAP. HRTEM images of T20/1.5LAP formulation with EDX outside (E) and inside (F) micelles. Schematic model and visual appearance of T1304 micelles (G).

3.5 Thermal analysis

To gain further understanding into these multi-component systems, thermal analysis of the samples was performed by **TG and DSC**. In the thermograms, BLPC presents two endothermic events (Fig. 6A1): a peak at 158°C, characteristic of its melting point, and an endothermic event at 230°C which coincides with 80% of mass loss in the TG curve (Fig. 6A2), indicating the thermal degradation of BLPC. These features are in agreement with those reported by Cunha-Filho et al. [61].

<Insert Fig. 6>

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3 Fig. 6. TG (1) and DSC (2) curves of the systems with and without BLPC. A) 1.5LAP,
 4 B) T10 and T10/1.5LAP, C) T20 and T20/1.5LAP.

5

6 The calorimetric curve of 1.5LAP (Fig. 6A1) presents an endothermic event with a wide
 7 peak around 100°C, that coincides with the mass loss of approximately 20% in the TG
 8 curve (Fig. 6A2), as result of its dehydration [62]. As expected for an inorganic mineral,
 9 the TG curve shows that LAP is thermostable, and the weight loss is related to the free
 10 water content in the clay. At 225 °C, below the temperature of drug degradation, the
 11 residual mass observed in the 1.5LAP/BLPC and 1.5LAP systems is 89% and 77.5%,
 12 respectively. Above this temperature, there is a greater weight loss in the 1.5LAP/BLPC
 13 system. Furthermore, in the presence of BLPC, the LAP dehydration event is no longer
 14 evident in the calorimetric curve (Fig. 6A1), suggesting that BLPC occupies the space
 15 where the water was previously free. In conclusion, these results support the hypothesis
 16 of the entrance of BLPC in the interlayer space of LAP [55,56].

17 According to previous studies [63], Tetric 1304 has a melting point without
 18 decomposition around 54°C, an event that is visible in the DSC curves of T10 (Fig. 6B1)
 19 and T20 (Fig. 6C1). Thermogravimetric curves of T10 and T20 show no mass loss up
 20 to 200°C, which correspond to the start of Tetric 1304 degradation (Fig. 6B2 and
 21 6C2). In the presence of LAP, an additional endothermic event is visible at 142°C,
 22 related to water loss (Fig. 6B1). This event is not observed for T20/1.5LAP, which may
 23 be due to the lower concentration of residual water generated by the lyophilization
 24 process in this sample and the higher concentration of Tetric than T10/1.5LAP.

25 Fig. 6B1 also presents a similar event but at a lower temperature (134 °C) for samples
 26 with BLPC due to an increase in the system's hydrophobic characteristics. On the other
 27 hand, this event disappeared for the T20/1.5LAP (Fig. 6C1), corroborating the TG curve
 28 (Fig. 6C2), where no mass loss is seen at 134 °C, suggesting a lower amount of water in
 29 these systems.

1 Mass loss in 1.5LAP is smaller than in formulations containing T1304 or unassociated
 2 BLPC from 225 °C to 335 °C due to the organic nature of these last substances, which
 3 degrade more easily. TG data indicate that both BLPC and T1304, when in hybrid
 4 systems, undergo degradation at much higher temperatures, suggesting higher thermal
 5 stability of the systems in the presence of LAP.

6 3.6 Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy

7 BLPC FTIR spectrum has already been reported in the literature [61,64] and is shown
 8 in Fig. S2 and S3 of the Supplementary Material. The red circles in Fig. 7 represent the
 9 characteristic bands mentioned in the text.

10 The spectrum from LAP presents a characteristic band at 1000 cm^{-1} , related to the Si-O
 11 bond widening [65]. The presence of BLPC in the system increased more than 2.2 times
 12 the transmittance related to this bond. Furthermore, the band at 1692 cm^{-1} , related to the
 13 C=O groups in BLPC, disappeared. This suggests a possible bonding of LAP with BLPC
 14 by carbonyl oxygen, forming a Si-O bond.

15 <Insert Fig. 7>

17 Fig. 7. FTIR spectra of BLPC and systems containing 1.5LAP, T10 and T10/1.5LAP,
 18 with and without BLPC. Characteristic bands and the bonds they represent are shown
 19 above the graph; red circles correspond to characteristic bands discussed in the text.

20
 21 The spectra of T1304 (T10) in Fig. 7 shows the characteristic band of poloxamines at
 22 1085 cm^{-1} [8], which corresponds to the C-O-C vibrations between the EO and PO
 23 groups. Bands at 2971 cm^{-1} and 2887 cm^{-1} [66] are due to symmetrical and asymmetric
 24 stretching of -CH₂ groups. The hybrids T10/1.5LAP (also Fig. 7) and T20/1.5LAP (Fig.
 25 S3, Supplementary Material) showed an increase in the band at 1000 cm^{-1} . Sun et al.
 26 [57] have shown that the adsorption of PEO-PPO polymers in LAP occurs through the
 27 PO groups, which may explain the increase in the Si-O binding band. No other changes
 28 are seen in the hybrid systems spectra. No change in the spectrum is noticed when BLPC
 29 is added to the hybrid systems, except for a decrease in the intensity of BLPC bands, but
 30 without evidence of the formation of new bonds, which could be an indication of the
 31 inclusion of the drug into the polymeric system [40].
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3.7 Cell assays

Fig. 8A and 8B show the results of cytotoxicity tests against healthy fibroblasts (3T3) and tumoral (MCF-7) cells respectively. At 8 $\mu\text{mol.L}^{-1}$, cell viability was brought to zero, hence the data are not shown. Fig. 8C shows a comparative summary of the cytotoxicity of LAP or hybrid systems in the presence or absence of BLPC, and Table 2 shows the concentration of BLPC necessary to decrease cell viability by 50% (IC_{50}) and the ratio between the IC_{50} of 3T3 cells and MCF-7, called the selectivity index (SI).
< Insert Fig. 8 >

10

11

(C)

Cells	Cell viability of formulations (%)					
	1.5LAP	1.5LAP +BLPC	T10/1.5LAP	T10/1.5LAP +BLPC	T20/1.5LAP	T20/1.5LAP +BLPC
3T3	6.7±1.9	27.6±1.9	3.0±0.3	43.1±3.1	-	-
MCF-7	-	-	29.7±5.1	8.7±0.5	16.4±4.4	37.1±10.0

Note: All formulations were diluted 1.3x. Formulations without BLPC have the equivalent weight concentration of the formulations with BLPC (samples with 6 $\mu\text{mol.L}^{-1}$ of BLPC's concentration).

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Fig. 8. Cytotoxicity tests in 3T3 (A) and MCF-7 (B) cells for BLPC and its formulation with 1.5LAP, T10/1.5LAP and T20/1.5LAP. (C) % cell viability in 3T3 and MCF-7 cell lines for formulations with and without BLPC. – data are not shown due to no statistically significant difference between samples with and without drug (n=6, mean \pm sd). *represents the statistical difference between groups with $p < 0.05$.

In 3T3 cell lines, a statistical difference in the treatments was only observed with a concentration of BLPC $6 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, when comparing free BLPC with 1.5LAP/BLPC and T10/1.5LAP/BLPC (the latter gave a cell viability 4 and 14 times higher, respectively, than free BLPC) (Fig.8C). Wang et al [67] reported that pristine LAP has no cytotoxic effect for 3T3 cells. However, the results presented at Fig. 8C show formulations without drug (1.5LAP, T10/1.5LAP) with higher toxicity, which expressive decreases in the presence of BLPC at $6 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ (1.5LAP+BLPC, T10/1.5LAP+BLPC).

Rey-Rico et al [68] demonstrated that Tetronic has some cytotoxic effect in 3T3 cells (viability of 40% for a concentration of 5% w/w). The viability of the T10/1.5LAP/BLPC is greater than that of 1.5LAP/BLPC, which could also suggest an even slower release of the drug in the hybrid systems. Release studies (next section) indeed show a very slow release taking place over up to 140 hours.

For cancer cell lines (MCF-7), the results shown in Fig. 8B are in accordance with previous studies by Pink et al (2000) [69] for BLPC values. In our study, the system that caused the least viability in tumoral cells was T10/1.5LAP/BLPC, which reduced cell viability at 2 to $6 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ compared to free BLPC at the same concentrations (p-value <0.05) (see also Fig. 8C). Besides, as seen in Fig. 8C, the T20/1.5LAP/BLPC hybrid system promoted a higher MCF-7 cells viability than T10/1.5LAP/BLPC, which, as suggested above, could be linked to higher retention of the drug and a slower release, consequently a weaker action on the target cells.

< Insert Table 2 >

Table 2. BLPC concentration ($\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) that inhibits 50% of cell growth (IC_{50}) in 3T3 and MCF-7 culture cells. Selectivity Index is the ratio between the IC_{50} in 3T3 cells and MCF-7 cells, (n=6, mean \pm sd).

Formulation	IC_{50} (μM)		Selectivity Index
	3T3	MCF-7	
BLPC	4.7 ± 0.8	3.7 ± 0.5	1.3
1.5LAP/BLPC	4.7 ± 0.9	3.437 ± 1.0	1.4
T10/1.5LAP/BLPC	3.9 ± 0.5	1.7 ± 0.2	2.2
T20/1.5LAP/BLPC	3.7 ± 0.1	5.0 ± 0.6	0.7

Table 2. shows the IC_{50} and selectivity indexes (SI) for free BLPC and formulated drug. SI values in the range of 0.7-1.4 for T20/1.5LAP, unassociated BLPC and 1.5LAP show that these systems are not selective towards tumoral cells, thus potentially toxic. Koch et al (2005) [70] consider that SI above 2 indicates that the analyzed substance has selectivity for use against diseased cells, a value reached only by T10/1.5LAP/BLPC nanohybrids; this is therefore the system we consider as the most promising for future experiments.

3.8 Release Assay

Based on all the results taken together, T10/1.5LAP/BLPC hybrid was taken forward for drug release studies (Fig. 9). BLPC is totally dissolved in the medium in approximately 6 hours. The slow-release profile of BLPC when incorporated in T10/1.5LAP/BLPC nanohybrids, hypothesized in previous sections, is confirmed by this experiment. Fig. 9A shows that T10/1.5LAP gel provides a controlled BLPC release for eight days (140 h). This is a remarkable sustained release, obtained because of the formation of a hybrid polymer-clay network at physiological temperature (37°C), which

1 shows strong viscoelastic properties (Fig. 2). This result, added to the selectivity index
 2 of this system towards cancer cells, and its sol-gel transition below body temperature,
 3 makes it a promising system to achieve the sustained release of BLPC over a very long
 4 time, possibly increasing the effectiveness of its action.

5 <Insert Fig. 9>

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 8 **Fig.9.** Cumulated release profile of BLPC and its formulation in T10/1.5LAP over 140
 9 hours (A) and mathematical models used to fit T10/1.5LAP/BLPC release kinetics (B).

10

11 Table 3 shows the parameters of different kinetic models applied to the data obtained
 12 from the drug cumulative release as a function of time (Fig. 9 A). For all models, %m is
 13 the percentage of BLPC released in the medium at time t (Fig. 9 B). The correlation
 14 coefficient, R² was calculated, and the results show fitted models with R² > 0.94.

15

16 <Insert Table 3>

17 **Table 3.** Equation, parameters and R² value for the best four mathematical models used
 18 to fit T10/1.5LAP/BLPC release kinetics.

Model	R ²	Equation	Parameters
Weibull	0.9610	$%m = 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{t^\beta}{\alpha}\right)}$	$\alpha = 148.750; \beta = 1.193$
Peppas-Sahlin	0.9619	$%m = ks1 \times t^{0.5} + ks2 \times t$	$ks1 = 3.40; ks2 = 0.52$
Hixson - Crowell	0.9755	$%m = 1 - (1 - khc \times t)^3$	$khc = 0.006$
Hopfenberg	0.9830	$%m = 1 - (1 - khb \times t)^{nh}$	$khp = 0.007; n = 2$

1
2 The data obtained for BLPC release from T10/1.5LAP (Fig. 9) shows a fit to the Weibull
3 model and $\beta > 1$. This β result is an indication of a complex process, with more than one
4 mechanism involved in the BLPC release [71]. With the Peppas-Sahlin model, the value
5 of ks_1 (Table 3) is remarkably higher than ks_2 . That is, the contribution of diffusion to
6 the BLPC release from the hybrid T10/1.5LAP system is higher than the influence of
7 polymer chain relaxation. The results of both models thus suggest that diffusion
8 probably plays the main role in the release of the drug, though other mechanisms should
9 not be disregarded.

10 The two models that best fitted the data are the Hixson-Crowell and Hopfenberg models
11 (Table 3). The first one applies to systems that undergo erosion and liberation of the
12 components. Similar to the Hixson-Crowell model, in the Hopfenberg model, erosion is
13 the predominant process responsible for the release of the drug. In this case, drug release
14 is explained either by the formation of new chemical bonds when in contact with the
15 drug release medium, or by drug dissolution in the release medium, with only the dry
16 polymeric matrix remaining at the end of the process [72]. The shape parameter “n”
17 (Table 3) is equal to 2, which predicts a cylindrical matrix. This can be associated with
18 the ability of Tetronics to form worm-like micelles identified in TEM images.

19 20 **4. Conclusion**

21 Given the low solubility and thus bioavailability of BLPC, the nanohybrid systems
22 reported here comprising the Tetronic 1304, a 4-arm PEO-PPO copolymer, with
23 laponite (LAP), are promising for the solubilisation of this drug and its sustained release
24 in injectable gels. These novel nanohybrids carriers promoted a 40-fold increase in
25 BLPC solubility. The presence of LAP improved the thermal stability of the drug, while
26 imparting a sol-gel transition below body temperature to the formulation. TEM images
27 of the nanoaggregates revealed for the first time the presence of flexible, cylindrical
28 T1304 micelles, which elongated further in the presence of LAP, presenting the
29 morphology of wormlike micelles, and could also contribute to the viscoelastic
30 properties, in addition to the largely invoked “house-of-cards” architectures found in
31 laponite gels. The biological evaluation of a range of formulations highlights a reduced
32 toxicity in BALB/3T3 fibroblast cells, and a good selectivity of T10/1.5LAP
33 formulations in MCF-7 mammary cancer cells. This specific formulation also afforded
34 a remarkable prolonged drug release for 140 hours. The Hixson-Crowell and
35 Hopfenberg kinetic models provided the best fits, suggesting that an erosion process
36 predominantly controls the release of the drug, associated with diffusion. The results
37 from this study provide a strong basis for the design of sustained-release pharmaceutical
38 formulations based on nanohybrids of Tetronic micelles and laponite, both widely
39 available and low-cost excipients with attractive characteristics.

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1 Disclosure statement

2 The authors declare that this research was conducted in the absence of any commercial
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- 10

1 **Supplementary material**

2 Fig. S1. Calibration curve of BLPC in ethanolic solution (1:1, v/v). The absorbance was
3 recorded and plotted a calibration curve against concentrations of drug, which followed
4 Beer's law and gave a straight line with $R^2 = 0.9998$ and equation $y = 0.1123x + 0.0041$.

5
6 Fig. S2. BLPC Infrared spectra and its characteristics bands.

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2 Fig. S3. Infrared spectra of the systems containing: LAP, T20 and T20/1.5LAP, with
3 and without BLPC.

4

5

1 Table captions

2 **Table 1:** Samples studied in this work comprising the polymeric surfactant Tetronic
3 T1304 with and without LAP, with concentrations ranging from 1-20% Tetronic and 0,
4 1.5 and 3% LAP.

5
6 **Table 2:** BLPC concentration ($\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) that inhibits 50% of cell growth (IC_{50}) in 3T3
7 and MCF-7 culture cells. Selectivity Index is the ratio between the IC_{50} in 3T3 cells and
8 MCF-7 cells, ($n=6$, mean \pm sd).

9
10 **Table 3:** Equation, parameters and R^2 value for the best four mathematical models used
11 to fit T10/1.5LAP/BLPC release kinetics.

12 Figure captions

13
14 **Scheme 1.** Synthesis of the BLPC by cyclization of Lapachol in acidic medium and
15 room temperature.

16
17 **Fig. 1.** Solubility of BLPC in formulations of T1304, LAP and their combination over
18 a range of concentrations, at room temperature. For hybrid systems (n) corresponds to
19 T1304 concentration and * represents the statistical difference between the groups with
20 $p < 0.05$. ($n=6$, mean \pm sd).

21
22 **Fig. 2.** Rheology temperature sweeps showing the elastic (G') and viscous (G'') moduli
23 for two formulations with and without BLPC. A) T10/1.5LAP. B) T20/1.5LAP. The
24 chart above each graph illustrates the phase behavior of the systems obtained from visual
25 observation. BLPC was incorporated at the maximum solubility obtained from the
26 solubility tests ($0.75 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ and $1.5 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$, respectively).

27
28 **Fig. 3.** The physical behavior of formulations at different concentrations after 1 week at
29 natural pH (~ 10) and at different temperatures.

30
31 **Fig. 4.** Intensity (%) size distributions of T1304 micelles as a function of temperature
32 (in $^{\circ}\text{C}$) obtained by DLS in H_2O (Milli-Q). In (A) T1, and (B) T10 formulations.

33
34 **Fig. 5.** Representative TEM and HRTEM images and of micellar morphologies
35 observed after drying an aqueous dispersion at 20°C . TEM images of: (A) T10 (B) T20,
36 (C) T10/1.5LAP (D) T20/1.5LAP. HRTEM images of T20/1.5LAP formulation with
37 EDX outside (E) and inside (F) micelles. Schematic model and visual appearance of
38 T1304 micelles (G).

39
40 **Fig. 6.** TG (1) and DSC (2) curves of the systems with and without BLPC. A) 1.5LAP,
41 B) T10 and T10/1.5LAP, C) T20 and T20/1.5LAP.

42
43 **Fig. 7.** FTIR spectra of BLPC and systems containing 1.5LAP, T10 and T10/1.5LAP,
44 with and without BLPC. Characteristic bands and the bonds they represent are shown
45 above the graph; red circles correspond to characteristic bands discussed in the text.

46
47 **Fig. 8.** Cytotoxicity tests in 3T3 (A) and MCF-7 (B) cells for BLPC and its formulation
48 with 1.5LAP, T10/1.5LAP and T20/1.5LAP. (C) % cell viability in 3T3 and MCF-7 cell
49 lines for formulations with and without BLPC. – data are not shown due to no

1 statistically significant difference between samples with and without drug (n=6, mean \pm
2 sd). *represents the statistical difference between groups with $p < 0.05$.

3
4 **Fig. 9.** Cumulated release profile of BLPC and its formulation in T10/1.5LAP over 140
5 hours (A) and mathematical models used to fit T10/1.5LAP/BLPC release kinetics (B).

6
7 **Supplementary Material Captions**

8
9 **Fig. S1.** Calibration curve of BLPC in ethanolic solution (1:1, v/v). The absorbance was
10 recorded and plotted a calibration curve against concentrations of drug, which followed
11 Beer's law and gave a straight line with $R^2 = 0.9998$ and equation $y = 0.1123x + 0.0041$.

12
13 **Fig. S2.** BLPC Infrared spectra and its characteristics bands.

14
15 **Fig. S3.** Infrared spectra of the systems containing: LAP, T20 and T20/1.5LAP, with
16 and without BLPC.

 β -Lapachone

(C)

Cells	Cell viability of formulations (%)					
	1.5LAP	1.5LAP +BLPC	T10/1.5LAP	T10/1.5LAP +BLPC	T20/1.5LAP	T20/1.5LAP +BLPC
3T3	6.7±1.9	27.6±1.9	3.0±0.3	43.1±3.1	-	-
MCF-7	-	-	29.7±5.1	8.7±0.5	16.4±4.4	37.1±10.0

Note: All formulations were diluted 1.3x. Formulations without BLPC have the equivalent weight concentration of the formulations with BLPC (samples with 6 $\mu\text{mol.L}^{-1}$ of BLPC's concentration).

Table 1: Samples studied in this work comprising the polymeric surfactant Tetronic T1304 with and without LAP, with concentrations ranging from 1-20% Tetronic and 0, 1.5 and 3% LAP.

Formulation		CODE
T1304 %, w/w	LAP %, w/w	
0	1.5	1.5LAP
0	3	3LAP
1	0	T1
5	0	T5
10	0	T10
15	0	T15
20	0	T20
1	1.5	T1/1.5LAP
5	1.5	T5/1.5LAP
10	1.5	T10/1.5LAP
15	1.5	T15/1.5LAP
20	1.5	T20/1.5LAP
1	3.0	T1/3LAP
5	3.0	T5/3LAP
10	3.0	T10/3LAP
15	3.0	T15/3LAP
20	3.0	T20/3LAP

Table 2: BLPC concentration ($\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) that inhibits 50% of cell growth (IC_{50}) in 3T3 and MCF-7 culture cells. Selectivity Index is the ratio between the IC_{50} in 3T3 cells and MCF-7 cells, (n=6, mean \pm sd).

Formulation	IC_{50} (μM)		Selectivity Index
	3T3	MCF-7	
BLPC	4.7 \pm 0.8	3.7 \pm 0.5	1.3
1.5LAP/BLPC	4.7 \pm 0.9	3.437 \pm 1.0	1.4
T10/1.5LAP/BLPC	3.9 \pm 0.5	1.7 \pm 0.2	2.2
T20/1.5LAP/BLPC	3.7 \pm 0.1	5.0 \pm 0.6	0.7

Table 3: Equation, parameters and R^2 value for the best four mathematical models used to fit T10/1.5LAP/BLPC release kinetics.

Model	R^2	Equation	Parameters
Weibull	0.9610	$\%m = 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{t^\beta}{\alpha}\right)}$	$\alpha = 148.750$; $\beta = 1.193$
Peppas-Sahlin	0.9619	$\%m = ks1 \times t^{0.5} + ks2 \times t$	$ks1 = 3.40$; $ks2 = 0.52$
Hixson - Crowell	0.9755	$\%m = 1 - (1 - khc \times t)^3$	$khc = 0.006$
Hopfenberg	0.9830	$\%m = 1 - (1 - khb \times t)^{nh}$	$khp = 0.007$; $n = 2$

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